

INITIAL PEDAGOGICAL PROCESSES IN THE DIRECTION OF PRIMARY EDUCATION STUDENTS TO THE PROFESSION

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the initial pedagogical processes in the direction of primary education students to the profession, and in this process the teacher's pedagogical skills, knowledge and skills related to the choice of profession, as well as personality traits in the choice of profession, the psychology of the reader, the criteria indicating the readiness of students to choose a profession, the content Methodological recommendations on the topic have been developed.*

Key words: *Teacher, pupil, primary education, profession, vocational orientation, psychology of young periods.*

НАЧАЛЬНЫЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПРОЦЕССЫ ПРИ НАПРАВЛЕНИИ УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССОВ К ПРОФЕССИИ

Аннотация. *в статье анализируются начальные педагогические процессы по направлению учащихся начальных классов к профессии, а также в этом процессе педагогические умения, знания и умения учителя, связанные с выбором профессии, а также особенности личности в выборе профессии. психология читателя, критерии, указывающие на готовность студентов к выбору профессии, содержание Разработаны методические рекомендации по теме.*

Ключевые слова: *Учитель, ученик, начальное образование, профессия, профессиональная направленность, психология юношеского возраста.*

In recent years, large-scale reforms are carried out in the education system of all spheres in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The result of these changes, the worthy place of our country among the developed countries, is first of all an integral link with the development of science and education. In order to further increase the effectiveness of the reforms carried out, create conditions for the comprehensive and accelerated development of the state and society, modernize our country and liberalize all spheres of life, the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated February 7, 2020 " on, tasks of the ministry for the development of Arts and sports, improvement of state policy on youth are defined.

It should be noted that the contribution of our teachers and trainers to the worthy perfection of our children, who possess modern knowledge and professional skills, foreign languages, are stepping into life with great hope and confidence and are the decisive force of our tomorrow, is incomparable. The teacher of primary education not only gives the students the initial knowledge of the world of science, but also the direction in which the students earn in this process. A pupil from childhood is fond of one profession, dreams of it, imagines himself as a person of the same profession. The teacher has a great role in ensuring the reality of this imagination. the teacher is a "wizard", an incomparable coach in the imagination of a child who is not yet perfectly formed. Materials And Methods All forms and techniques of work carried out in the direction of primary education students to the profession should serve the purposeful career choice of the students.

When conducting vocational orientation work in school, it is recommended to use new elements of pedagogical technology, such as pedagogical play, independent thoughts, along with traditional practical training, conversation, dialogue discussions. Primary education students are still far from choosing a profession. However, the work of choosing the right profession among them should be such a basis that the interests, mind and intentions of the students in the upper classes will later develop on the basis of this basis.

The qualities of a person who are necessary and important for all professions, these are: - Diligence, respect for the people of labor in all professions and specialties; - Understanding and understanding the need to work; - being able to plan and control their work; - being able to properly organize the workplace, sink into work and be disciplined; – Ability to choose the most rational way of coping, persistence, task execution. Materials are well time saving and the like. All these qualities and qualities should be formulated in the students from the first grade. The teacher in the process of observing the student in the lessons, talking with him, analyzing the performance of the child activity, perceives some of its features, inclinations, after fulfilling the corresponding work on the development of these qualities; these can then be the main factor in determining the profession. In order to choose a profession, the reader must have the ability to evaluate his abilities that is, the mind, interest, knowledge of various professions, the possibilities of these professions, and information about the future.

Orientation of the individual to the profession is carried out through special scientific practical activities, at the stages of the formation of students as a person, the person and society, that is, the family, is considered as a single system, the requirements of market economy relations are taken into account in the transition period. Criteria indicating the willingness of students to choose a profession: – cognitive (having information); - criteria of interest in the profession; - practical criterion. In order for the right choice of profession to be suitable for the weather, interests, inclinations, abilities and opportunities of each growing generation, it is necessary to take into account its health, assimilation and feelings, which in social useful and productive labor are expressed and manifested more than everyone else. And the early detection of important professional qualities of the child can later give him the opportunity to choose the right profession according to his characteristics successfully master it, achieve high results in labor. Work on this is carried out according to a pre-established plan. According to this plan, the most popular professions for organizing an excursion are planned to organize conversations for students of rural schools in a collective farm, for students of urban schools in enterprises, in the work of parents and in the success they have achieved in their labor.

During the extortions, the main attention is paid to the labor of the people involved in the production process, the weapons of labor that they give to obtaining finished products from raw materials; the role of labor in the life of society and some people is studied. The Second Stage (VVII) working with students of classes is a stage that motivates them to do anything. It is known that in the educational process, interest in knowledge in students is usually formed before the interest in the profession. Therefore, in the work carried out in the field of vocational orientation at this stage, it is important to arouse interest in students to know the types of work (work with techniques, work with natural objects, etc.). At this stage of professional orientation, extracurricular activities, quizzes, games related to technique and labor (technical creativity and

agricultural experimentation) should play a big role. At this stage, the formation of social goals in students will continue, at the same time vocational orientation will also begin. The third stage (mainly VIII-XI) covers the pupils of classes — at this stage, students examine their forces in concrete Labor, the interests and inclinations of students to the profession are more formed.

At this stage, students strengthen their own professional intentions with practical skills and skills in some general professions. This stage ends with the selection of a concrete profession, the designation of ways to master it. It is noteworthy for this stage that the students work in circles on their interests (subjects, subject-technique, productiontechnique, etc.).

The following suggestions are recommended to further improve the process of vocational orientation of primary education students.

- focus on individual work in the direction of the profession; – Organization of round tables on the topic;
- Acquaintance with audio – video materials of different professions; – Orientation of extracurricular work to the choice of professions;
- Organization of meetings with specialists of different spheres; – Organization of cultural events;
- Organization of the corner of professions and organization of portable displays on the same subject.

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